

Quinonoid constituents from some Bignoniaceae plants

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Isolation of lapachol, tecomaquinone-I, 2-isopropenyl naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone, dehydroiso- α -lapachone and dehydro- α -lapachone from the roots of *Tabebuia rosea*; lapachol, dehydroiso- α -lapachone, dehydro- α -lapachone from the stem-heartwood of *Stereospermum suaveolens*; and lapachol, tecomaquinone-I, dehydro- α -lapachone, α -lapachone, stigmaterol, β -sitosterol and β -lapachone are reported from the sap-wood of *Heterophragma adenophyllum*.

Tabebuia rosea DC. is grown as an ornamental tree in gardens. It is a tall, erect and deciduous tree reaching upto 20 m. Rosea is in allusion to the rosy colour of flowers. Earlier work done on this plant led to the isolation of some naphthoquinone derivatives from its stem-heartwood¹ and bark². *Stereospermum suaveolens* DC. is a tall evergreen tree up to 15 m in height. It is used as a local remedy for different diseases³. Its root bark is used in an Indian tonic preparation 'Dasamula'. The work on its roots and leaves reported the isolation of quinones⁴ and flavone glycosides^{5,6}, but no systematic work has been reported from its stem-heartwood. *Heterophragma adenophyllum* is a large evergreen ornamental tree grown in tropical and subtropical climates. Its root is prescribed as drink in viper-bite and its wood tar used in various skin diseases⁷. Some quinone derivatives have been reported⁸ from the heartwood of the plant.

The present communication reports the isolation and characterization of lapachol, tecomaquinone-I, 2-isopropenyl naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone, dehydroiso- α -lapachone and dehydro- α -lapachone from the roots of *T. rosea*; lapachol, dehydroiso- α -lapachone, dehydro- α -lapachone from the stem-heartwood of *S. suaveolens*; and lapachol, tecomaquinone-I, dehydro- α -lapachone, α -lapachone, stigmaterol, β -sitosterol and β -lapachone from the sap-wood of *H. adenophyllum*.

Results and Discussion

Tabebuia rosea :

The pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the roots of *T. rosea* was separated into acidic and neutral fractions using 2 *N* Na₂CO₃ solution. The acidic fraction yielded lapachol whereas the neutral fraction gave tecomaquinone-I, 2-isopropenyl naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone, dehydroiso- α -lapachone and dehydro- α -lapachone.

Lapachol was isolated as yellow shining needles, m.p. 139–140°. It showed the colour reactions characteristic of a quinonoid compound with chelated hydroxyl group. Its IR spectrum showed important absorption bands at 3350 (chelated hydroxyl group) and 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Its ¹H NMR spectrum displayed a pair of singlets at δ 1.73 and 1.82 for two olefinic methyl groups. A downfield triplet at δ 5.27 and a broad doublet at 3.35 corresponded to =CH and -CH₂- protons of prenyl side-chain, respectively, while aromatic protons gave multiplets centered at δ 7.81 and 8.11. Its mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 242 corresponding to its molecular formula C₁₅H₁₄O₃.

Tecomaquinone-I was obtained from the neutral fraction as blue-green crystals, m.p. 198–199° after crystallization with methanol. Earlier the quinone was named as dehydrotectol⁹. Its structure was revised¹⁰ and renamed as tecomaquinone-I. Its IR spectrum exhibited the presence of conjugated carbonyl stretching frequencies at 1664 and 1650 cm⁻¹. Its ¹H NMR spectrum revealed the presence of two singlets at δ 1.64 and 1.66 for geminal methyl pair and doublets at δ 5.58, 6.16 and 6.42 for three vinylic protons. The former two doublets coupled together with coupling constant *J* 10 Hz indicate their *cis*-configuration. In addition, there was a doublet multiplet at δ 5.45 coupled to the doublet at δ 6.42 and allylically coupled to olefinic methyl doublets at δ 1.60 and 2.05. The multiplets for aromatic protons were centered at δ 7.50, 7.72 and 8.15. Molecular ion peak at *m/z* 448 confirmed its molecular formula C₃₀H₂₄O₄.

2-Isopropenyl naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone was obtained as yellow coloured crystalline compound, m.p. 172–173°. This quinone was earlier isolated from *Radermachera sinica*¹¹ and *Markhamia hildebrandtii*¹². Its IR spectrum displayed bands at 1660 and 1655 cm⁻¹ corresponding to conjugated carbonyl groups. Its ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃)

showed two broad singlets at δ 5.35 and 5.94 corresponding to vinyl protons and another broad singlet at δ 2.14 corresponded to the methyl group of the side-chain. A singlet at δ 6.83 was due to the methine proton of the furan ring. The aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at δ 7.50 and 8.37.

Dehydroiso- α -lapachone was obtained as golden yellow flakes, m.p. 102–103°. Its IR spectrum showed conjugated carbonyl stretching bands at 1667 and 1637 cm^{-1} . Its UV spectrum gave important bands at 253, 295 and 342 nm. Its ^1H NMR spectrum displayed two double doublets at δ 2.94 and 3.21 corresponding to methylene protons of dihydrofuran ring while another double doublet at δ 5.38 due to methine proton of the same ring. Above signals exhibited the characteristic ABX splitting pattern. In addition, a singlet was present at δ 1.67 corresponding to olefinic methyl group while two vinyl protons resonated at δ 5.02 as doublet. Multiplets were present at δ 7.68 and 8.07 for aromatic protons.

Dehydro- α -lapachone was isolated as orange needles, m.p. 143–144°. Its IR spectrum showed important peaks at 1681 and 1640 cm^{-1} . Its ^1H NMR spectrum exhibited a singlet at δ 1.56 integrated for six protons of geminal methyl groups. A pair of downfield doublets at δ 5.76 (J 10 Hz) and 6.87 (J 10 Hz) indicated the *cis*-geometry of the H-3 and H-4 olefinic protons. The aromatic protons gave multiplets centered at δ 7.82 and 8.10. These spectral data indicated it to be dehydroiso- α -lapachone.

Stereospermum suaveolens :

The concentrated benzene extract of the heartwood was treated in the similar way with 2 *N* Na_2CO_3 solution, which afforded lapachol from acidic and dehydroiso- α -lapachone and dehydro- α -lapachone from neutral fraction respectively.

Heterophragma adenophyllum :

Its acetone extract was separated into acidic and neutral portions with 2 *N* Na_2CO_3 solution to yield lapachol from acidic portion and tecomaquinone-I, dehydro- α -lapachone, α -lapachone, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol and β -lapachone from its neutral portion.

α -Lapachone was isolated as pale yellow needles, m.p. 117–118°. Its IR spectrum showed important absorption peaks at 1678 and 1640 cm^{-1} . Its UV spectrum revealed peaks at 251, 281, 332 and 375 nm. Its ^1H NMR spectrum showed a singlet at δ 1.47 integrated for six protons of two methyl groups. A pair of triplets was centered at δ 1.87 and 2.72 (J 7 Hz each) assigned to the two methylene groups. The multiplets at δ 7.90 and 8.26 corresponded to aromatic protons. Molecular ion peak at m/z 242 corresponded to its molecular formula $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$.

Stigmasterol was isolated as colourless needles, m.p.

166–167°, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ and identified by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 144–145°. β -Sitosterol was also obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 136–137°, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ and identified by its co-TLC with authentic sample.

β -Lapachone was obtained as red needles, m.p. 154–155°. Its ^1H NMR spectrum showed a singlet at δ 1.51 for two geminal methyl groups. A pair of triplets centered at δ 1.87 and 2.63 corresponded to two methylene groups of dihydropyran ring. The multiplets at δ 7.77 and 8.22 were due to aromatic protons. Molecular ion peak at m/z 242 indicated its molecular formula as $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$.

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected. ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on DRX-300 instrument at 300 MHz using TMS as internal standard, UV spectra on a Hitachi U-200 spectrophotometer, IR spectra on a Magna IR-550 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer.

The finely powdered roots (2 kg) of *T. rosea* were extracted with pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°) (3 \times 12 h) over a steam-bath. The resulting extract was concentrated to dryness and then taken into ether. The ethereal extract was treated with 2 *N* Na_2CO_3 solution. The sodium carbonate soluble fraction (acidic fraction) was then treated with 6 *N* HCl to get yellow coloured lapachol (100 mg). Sodium carbonate insoluble part (neutral fraction) was washed, dried and chromatographed over neutral alumina (deactivated with 10% aqueous AcOH) to give fraction-1 (pet. ether), fraction-2 (pet. ether-benzene, 1 : 1), fraction-3 (benzene), fraction-4 (benzene-ethyl acetate, 1 : 1), fraction-5 (ethyl acetate) and fraction-6 (ethyl acetate-methanol, 1 : 1). Fraction-1 afforded tecomaquinone-I (25 mg) after crystallization from methanol. Fraction-2 on silica gel preparative TLC (pet. ether-benzene, 1 : 1) gave 2-isopropenyl-naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (15 mg), fraction-3 showed a single spot on TLC plate and yielded dehydroiso- α -lapachone as golden yellow flakes (18 mg). Fraction-4 on preparative TLC (benzene) afforded orange needles, identified as dehydro- α -lapachone (30 mg). Fraction-5 and -6 were complex mixture of compounds, which could not be purified further due to paucity of material.

The air-dried shavings (5 kg) of stem-heartwood of *S. suaveolens* were extracted on a steam-bath (3 \times 12 h) and the extract was concentrated to dryness and taken in ether. The ethereal solution was separated in acidic and neutral fractions using 2 *N* Na_2CO_3 solution. The acidic fraction afforded lapachol (200 mg) whereas the neutral fraction was chromatographed over neutral alumina to give 4 fractions; fraction-1 (pet. ether), fraction-2 (pet. ether-benzene, 1 : 1), fraction-3 (benzene) and fraction-4 (benzene-ethyl acetate, 1 : 1). Fraction-1 and -2 could not be purified being a complex mixture of several compounds with a meagre amount

of material. Fraction-3 on crystallization with pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1) afforded dehydroiso- α -lapachone (25 mg). Fraction-4 on preparative TLC (benzene) gave orange needles of dehydro- α -lapachone (65 mg).

The coarsely powdered air-dried sapwood shavings (3 kg) of *H. adenophyllum* were extracted with acetone (3 \times 12 h) on a steam-bath and the resulting extract was concentrated to dryness. The separation of extract in acidic and neutral fractions was carried out by adopting similar procedure as described in case of earlier plants. The acidic fraction yielded lapachol (120 mg) while neutral fraction was chromatographed over deactivated alumina yielding 6 fractions : fraction-1 (pet. ether), fraction-2 (pet. ether-benzene, 1 : 1), fraction-3 (benzene), fraction-4 (benzene-ethyl acetate, 4 : 1), fraction-5 (benzene-ethyl acetate, 1 : 1) and fraction-6 (ethyl acetate). Fraction-1 afforded tecomaquinone-I (20 mg) on crystallization from methanol. Fraction-2 gave an orange mass which on purification with preparative TLC gave dehydro- α -lapachone (35 mg). Fraction-3 gave a yellow mass which on crystallization with pet. ether-chloroform (1 : 1) gave α -lapachone (15 mg). Fraction-4 showed 2 spots on TLC (on spraying with 10% H₂SO₄) and separated by preparative TLC (benzene) giving stigmaterol (30 mg) and β -sitosterol (25 mg). Fraction-5 gave orange needles (22 mg) and identified as β -lapachone.

Fraction-6 could not be worked due to paucity of material.

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